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Yakup Civelek - Sami Baskın

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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybider Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 13 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Krallık, Cezayir, Çin, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 72'i Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 80'i farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 152 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta bilim insanlarının kongrede sunduğu bildirilerin tam metinlerine yer verilmiştir. Bu sunumların geniş kitlelere ulaşarak alana faydalı olmasını ve yeni çalışmalara ilham vermesini diliyorum.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Yakup Civelek
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يأتي هذا الكتاب نتيجًا لجهود مجموعة من الباحثين البارزين الذين شاركوا بأبحاثهم في المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، والذي عُقد في أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. يعد هذا المؤتمر أحد أبرز الفعاليات الأكاديمية التي تجمع بين مختلف التخصصات في مجال العلوم الإنسانية، حيث شارك فيه باحثون من أكثر من عشرين دولة من مختلف القارات، مما أضفى طابعًا عالميًا ومتنوعًا على المناقشات التي جرت.

تميز المؤتمر بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي الذي انعكس في الأوراق البحثية المقدمة، حيث تناول الباحثون قضايا متعددة تشمل الأدب الكلاسيكي والمعاصر، اللغات الحديثة والقديمة، ودراسات الثقافة وتأثيراتها على المجتمعات المختلفة. ولم يقتصر النقاش على دراسة الأعمال الأدبية أو تحليل النصوص اللغوية فحسب، بل تطرق إلى استكشاف العلاقة بين اللغة والثقافة وكيف تساهم في تشكيل الهويات الفردية والجماعية.

تمحورت العديد من الأبحاث حول قضايا مثل تأثير العولمة على اللغات والثقافات المحلية، وكيفية المحافظة على التراث الثقافي واللغوي في مواجهة التغيرات المتسارعة. كما سلطت الأبحاث الضوء على دور الأدب في نقل التجارب الإنسانية والتعبير عن القضايا الاجتماعية والسياسية، ما أضاف أبعادًا جديدة لفهمنا للأدب كوسيلة للتغيير الاجتماعي والثقافي. في هذا السياق، عُرضت دراسات معمقة حول الترجمة ودورها في بناء جسور بين الثقافات المختلفة، حيث كانت الترجمة موضوعًا محوريًا في العديد من الأبحاث التي ناقشت التحديات التي تواجه المترجمين في نقل النصوص بما يحافظ على أصالتها وسياقها الثقافي. وقد أضافت هذه الأبحاث أبعادًا جديدة للفهم العالمي للأدب واللغة كوسائل لتبادل الأفكار والتجارب بين الشعوب.

من الجدير بالذكر أن المؤتمر تناول أيضًا التحولات التي تشهدها اللغات والأدب في العصر الرقمي، حيث تم تسليط الضوء على تأثير التكنولوجيا الحديثة على كيفية إنتاج النصوص الأدبية وتلقيها. وقدمت أبحاث حول كيفية توظيف الأدوات الرقمية في تحليل النصوص الأدبية، مما أتاح فرصًا جديدة للتفاعل مع الأدب بطرق مبتكرة ومختلفة.

هذا الكتاب يضم بين صفحاته نتائج عمل أكاديمي متميز يُظهر مدى التنوع والغنى الفكري الذي تمتعت به فعاليات هذا المؤتمر. فالأوراق البحثية المنشورة هنا ليست مجرد عرض لقضايا أدبية أو لغوية، بل هي محاولات جادة لاستكشاف العلاقات العميقة بين النصوص، الثقافات، والمجتمعات، وكيف يمكن أن يساهم فهم هذه العلاقات في تعزيز التواصل بين الشعوب في زمن يشهد فيه العالم تحديات متزايدة تتعلق بالتنوع الثقافي واللغوي.

نأمل أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة غنية للنقاشات العلمية حول اللغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية، وأن يكون محفزًا لمزيد من البحوث التي تسعى لفهم أعمق لتلك التخصصات الإنسانية التي تعد جزءًا أساسيًا من تشكيل هوياتنا وفهمنا للعالم. وختامًا، نود أن نعبر عن شكرنا لكل الباحثين الذين أسهموا بأبحاثهم في هذا المؤتمر، وكذلك لجميع الجهات المنظمة والداعمة التي ساهمت في إنجاح هذا الحدث الأكاديمي المتميز.

İçindekiler - فهرس - Contents

Kutadgu Bilig’de Kalem ve Kılıç	377
Doç. Dr. Salih Demirbilek	
Türk Müziği Solfej Eğitiminde Deşifre Becerilerini Geliştirmek İçin Bir Öneri: Dört Adım Yaklaşımı	386
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Çağlar Toptaş	
Arap Alfabesinde Harflerin Dizilişi ve Alfabe Öğretimine İlişkin Bazı Sorunlar	396
Doç. Dr. Nazife Nihal İnce	
Bitki ve Hayvan Örnekleme Bağlamında “Kitâb-ı Atalar Sözi”ndeki Sembolizm Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme	405
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Muhammed Avşar	
Siyâveş-İ Kısırâyî nin <i>Gazel Berayî Direht</i> (Ağaca Gazel) Şiirine Bir Bakış.....	436
Arş. Gör. Dr. Dilek Sakaroğlu	
444	محاكاة المقامة الحديثة للمقامة التراثية - المقامة الحلبية لليازجي نموذجاً
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Nadir Menderes	
<i>Göçmen Bavulu</i> Metaforu Üzerinden Gerçekleştirilen Sanatsal İfadeler	457
Dr. Evrim Kabukcu	

- Göçün Feminizasyonu: *Kadınların Göç Hafızası Örneği*..... 467
Dr. Evrim Kabukcu
- Religious Fanaticism and Colonial Vulnerability in Marlon James's *John Crow's Devil: An Exploration of Internal Conflict and External Domination*..... 476
Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş
19. Yüzyıl Âşık Şiirinde Ferhat ile Şirin Hikâyesi Bağlamında İntihar Temi..... 489
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan
- Dijital Kültür Bağlamında 21. Yüzyıl Âşıklarına Ait Facebook Cönkleri..... 497
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Şeyma Mert
- Semîn El-Halebî'nin Ed-Dürrü'l-Masûn Fî 'Ulûmi'l-Kitâbi'l-Meknûn İsimli Eserinde Züheyr B. Ebi Sülmâ'nın Muallakasından Yapılan İstîşadlar Üzerine Bir İnceleme..... 509
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Ayşe Sena Ünlü
Doç. Dr. Bünyamin Aydın
- Yabancılara Türkçe Öğretiminde İsimlerde Tümleme Yapılarının Edinimi..... 523
Lisansüstü Öğrencisi Kübra Bahar
- Palestinian Narratives of Displacement and Resistance: A Postcolonial Reading..... 539
Dr. Taghreed Gamal Elbakly

558.....التواصل اللغوي بين العربية والفارسية مظاهر تأثير العربية في الفارسية نموذجاً

عبد الكريم جرادات

The Interplay of Power and Corruption in Hanya Yanagihara's *The People in the Trees* through a Foucauldian Lens 572

Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş

Tara June Winch'in *The Yield* Romanında Kültürel Asimilasyon Bağlamında Dilin ve Kültürel Mirasın Korunması..... 581

Doç. Dr. Mehmet Recep Taş

Tuva Türkçesinde Sözlüksel Ettirgenlik İşaretleyicilerinin Kullanımı 588

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Tuğba Sarıkaya Aksoy

Türkçede Yaygın Olarak Kullanılan Arapça Kelimelerin Yapısı ve Sistematiği 596

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Yakup Eroğlu

Kırık Hayatlar Romanında Güzel ve Yüce Üzerine..... 614

Arş. Gör. Dr. Zeynep Şener

630.....البنية الصرفية للمشتقات في الشعر الصوفي وأثرها في توجيه المعنى الرواس نموذجاً

Dr. Öğr. Üyesi M. Salem Assad

638.....التواصل اللغوي بين العربية والفارسية: مظاهر تأثير العربية في الفارسية نموذجاً

عبد الكريم جرادات

Palestinian Narratives of Displacement and Resistance: A Postcolonial Reading

Dr. Taghreed Gamal Elbakly

Assistant Professor of English Literature, Shaqra' University, KSA

Abstract

This paper delves into the intricate tapestry of Palestinian fiction, examining how Palestinian authors narrate the profound experiences of displacement and resistance through a postcolonial lens. Reading selected Palestinian novels, this research probes into the manner in which these narratives subvert colonial rhetoric, unravel the intricacies of power relations, and scrutinize the formation of Palestinian identity. These explorations collectively contribute to a renewed understanding of Palestine within the contemporary context of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Through a postcolonial lens, this study provides a sophisticated comprehension of the Palestinian quest for emancipation and autonomy, underscoring the long-term Coercion of colonialism upon Palestinian social and cultural fabric.

Keywords: Palestinian novel, postcolonial theory, displacement, resistance, identity, colonialism, power dynamics

سرديات التهجير والمقاومة: قراءة في الرواية الفلسطينية ما بعد الاستعمار

د. تغريد جمال البقلي

أستاذ الأدب الإنجليزي المساعد، جامعة شقراء، المملكة العربية السعودية

الملخص

تهدف هذه الورقة البحثية إلى إمعان النظر في نسيج الرواية الفلسطينية المعقد، وتدرس كيف يروي المؤلفون الفلسطينيون تجارب التهجير والمقاومة في ضوء نظرية ما بعد الاستعمار. ومن خلال قراءة روايات فلسطينية مختارة، يعرض البحث الطريقة التي أبطلت بها هذه الروايات نمطية الخطاب الاستعماري، وكشف تعقيدات ديناميات القوى، وإعادة تشكيل الهوية الفلسطينية. تتضافر هذه العوامل في إعادة قراءة فلسطين تجديد فهم إطار المقاومة الفلسطينية ضمن السياق المعاصر للصراع الفلسطيني الإسرائيلي. تطرح هذه الدراسة فهماً متطوراً للسعي الفلسطيني للتحرر والحكم الذاتي، كردود طبيعي للتأثير المتواتر للاستعمار على المجتمع والثقافة الفلسطينية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الرواية الفلسطينية، نظرية ما بعد الاستعمار، التهجير، المقاومة، الهوية، الاستعمار، ديناميات القوة

Introduction

Between the Lines: Unmasking Colonial Power, Remapping the Margins

The question of Palestine is therefore the contest between an affirmation and a denial, and it is this prior contest, dating back over a hundred years, which animates and makes sense of the current impasse between the Arab states and Israel. The contest has been almost comically uneven from the beginning.

— Edward W. Said, *The Question of Palestine*, p18

Postcolonial theory offers a critical lens through which to examine the enduring legacies of European colonialism. It challenges the Eurocentric narrative, foregrounding the experiences and perspectives of colonized peoples. By interrogating the historical and contemporary manifestations of imperial power, postcolonial theory seeks to dismantle colonial discourses and to envision a more equitable and just world. It has significantly influenced literary and cultural studies, prompting a re-evaluation of canonical texts and a greater appreciation for marginalized voices.

Postcolonial theory interrogates the enduring impact of colonialism, examining how its legacies persist beyond formal imperial rule. Gandhi (2019) advocates that “the postcolonial condition is inaugurated with the onset rather than the end of colonial occupation” (p.3). It explores the ongoing struggle against neocolonial power and envisions a future liberated from its oppressive structures. Ball (2012) suggests, “a key premise of postcolonialism has been the construction of a discursive space that resists hegemonic colonial narratives by shifting the marginalised voices of the colonised from the peripheries to the centre of cultural consciousness.” (p.3). Postcolonialism effectively explores the intricate interplay between historical colonialism and contemporary power dynamics, emphasizing the persistence of colonial legacies and the ongoing quest for liberation.

Zionist hegemony has suppressed Palestinian voices within both political and cultural discourse, thereby obstructing a comprehensive postcolonial analysis of the Palestinian experience. While Edward Said's work has significantly shaped postcolonial studies, his writings on Palestine, such as *The Question of Palestine* and *After the Last Sky*, have relatively been overlooked; this oversight underscores the enduring hegemony of Zionist narratives within academic discourse. Said's *The Question of Palestine* provides a stark and unadorned demonstration of Orientalism's pernicious influence. While Orientalism subtly alludes to Palestine's subjugation, *The Question of Palestine* directly dissects the systems of power and knowledge that have historically marginalized and dispossessed the Palestinian people.

The 1948 Nakba stands as a harrowing testament in that context. Said's analysis of Balfour's speeches exposes the insidious underbelly of Orientalism. By deploying Orientalist tropes, Balfour rationalized the dispossession of Palestinians. Said, 2003, pp.31-33). The dehumanizing rhetoric employed by colonial powers, including the characterization of Palestine as a "diseased" land in need of a "surgical operation," served as a rhetorical device to justify the brutal dispossession and subjugation of the indigenous Palestinian population. (Gregory, 2004, p.81). Williams (2010) argues that postcolonialism is “an ‘anticipatory’ discourse, looking forward to a better and as yet unrealized world by contrast from one where colonialism has not been eradicated” (p.93).

The Zionist narrative, a specter haunting Western discourse, has distorted perceptions of the Palestinian struggle. Masalha (2014) genuinely exposes the insidious rhetoric employed by the imperialist Zionist narrative stating:

Zionist mission civilisatrice cultivated the myth of Israel as a “democratic outpost” of European enlightenment in the Middle East, surrounded by a backward Islamic “Orient”. The foundational narratives of Zionism, often repeated ad nauseam in the Western media, describe Israel as an “exceptional state”: a state born miraculously shortly after the horrific Nazi Holocaust and against all odds; an enlightened “liberal democracy”, in fact the “only democracy in the Middle East”, in a backward region, surrounded by a “tough neighbourhood.” (pp.64-65)

The potent power of Zionist propaganda through its denial of the Nakba and the whitewashing of Israel's actions have created a distorted reality, hindering the pursuit of justice and reconciliation. “[C]olonialism is not satisfied merely with holding a people in its grip and emptying the native’s brain of all form and content. By a kind of perverted logic, it turns to the past of the oppressed people, and distorts, disfigures, and destroys it.” (Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, p.210). The silencing of Palestine, a deliberate act of cultural genocide, has taken on insidious forms, often driven by political and cultural machinations. As Ball (2012) notes, Academic and creative freedom is often curtailed by various constraints “when it comes to the task of formulating critical or *imaginative* accounts of Palestinian history, culture and identity” (p.2). Salman Rushdie observes that “any attempt to provide a critique of Zionism is faced, particularly nowadays, with the charge that it is anti-Semitism in disguise” (Cited in Moore Gilbert, 2016, p.12).

The weaponization of anti-Semitism functions as a tool of silencing, stifling critical discourse on Israel-Palestine. The tragic assassinations of Palestinian intellectuals such as Ghassan Kanafani in 1972 and Naji al-Ali in 1987 highlight the perilous consequences of speaking truth to power. Such acts of violence, exacerbated by the Israeli authorities' imposition of publishing restrictions, constitute a form of ‘cultural genocide’, as coined by Raphael Lemkin, (Masalha, 2012, p.11) or, as Moore-Gilbert terms it, ‘culturecide.’ (2016, p.26). The enduring Nakba, the catastrophic expulsion of Palestinians from their homeland, remains a poignant testament to this cultural erasure and a harbinger of even greater cultural annihilation. By acknowledging these historical and contemporary methods of silencing, we can comprehend the profound significance of cultural resistance and the urgent need to elevate Palestinian voices. Despite facing relentless oppression, Palestinian artists, writers, and intellectuals have persevered, their work a testament to the indomitable human spirit.

According to postcolonial criticism, nations are narrations (Said, 1994a, p.xiii; Bhabha, 2004, p.201). This also echoes Anderson's assertion that the novel plays a pivotal role in constructing and reinforcing national identities. (1991, p.25). Critics such as Gayatri Spivak underscore the imperative of safeguarding cultural memory as a crucial act of resistance against colonial domination. As Spivak argues in “*Can the Subaltern Speak?*” (1988), the postcolonial intellectual must strive to amplify the voices of the marginalized and should exert every “effort to give the subaltern a voice in history” (p.92). Through this lens, novels like *Mornings in Jenin* and *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* (“*Thorns and Carnations*”) align with Spivak's call to empower marginalized voices, offering literary testimony to the Palestinian refugee experiences.

Another model of postcolonial resistance involves challenging the dominance of colonial power structures that Homi Bhabha (1995) conceptualizes as a “third space of enunciation.”

This space subverts, “the binary thought and essentialist identities produced by colonial knowledge” (Bhabha, 1995, p. 276). With his concept of hybridity, Bhabha examines, “the psychic and cultural fault-lines which are generated around and constantly threaten, any simple ‘black-and-white’ distinction between two conventional parties to the colonial relationship” (Boehmer, 2006, p. 355). Here, Nostalgia serves as a potent force in fueling Palestinian resistance. By anchoring individuals to their cultural heritage and fostering a sense of collective belonging, nostalgia provides a powerful antidote to the disorienting effects of displacement and dispossession. It offers solace in the face of adversity, enabling Palestinians to navigate the challenges of exile and occupation. Through the integration of past and present, nostalgia facilitates a process of cultural and psychological resilience, allowing individuals to reconcile personal growth with collective trauma.

The deliberate selection of *Mornings in Jenin* and *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* as focal points for a postcolonial reading of Palestinian fiction offers a profound exploration of resistance and displacement. These novels, imbued with the raw power of lived experience, delve into the heart of the Palestinian struggle, challenging dominant narratives and humanizing the Palestinian experience. *Mornings in Jenin* lays bare the brutality of the Israeli invasion, while *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* delves into the psychological and emotional scars of displacement and exile. Both novels resonate with postcolonial themes, offering a powerful critique of colonial power and a testament to the enduring human spirit.

Echoes of the Past: Nostalgia and Resistance in *Mornings in Jenin*

Today, Jenin, the city and the refugee camp, is embodied in every Palestinian... Rest assured that the children of Jenin, those who made it out of the rubble of their homes will never forget. Never remain silent. How can they while Jenin continues screaming for help?

—Ramzy Baroud, *Searching Jenin: Eyewitness Accounts of the Israeli Invasion*, p.235

Mornings in Jenin (2010) by Susan Abulhawa stands as a poignant testament to the Palestinian experience, a literary tapestry woven from the threads of history. It traverses the tumultuous landscape of Palestine, from the cataclysmic Nakba of 1948 to the subsequent Naksa of 1967, the harrowing Sabra and Shatila massacre, and the tragic Jenin massacre of 2002. Abulhawa transcends mere historical recounting, delving into the depths of human emotion to convey the collective trauma of the Palestinian people, individualized and amplified.

In such evocative work, *Mornings in Jenin*, Abulhawa delves into the profound impact of the 1948 Nakba, a cataclysmic event that inflicted upon the Palestinian people the twin scourges of violent dispossession and subjugation. A scrutiny reading of the novel probes the intricate tapestry of historical, political, and gendered threads woven into a refugee narrative and an exile chronicle. The novel's evocative depiction of longing for home, particularly through the symbolic resonance of land, trees, and harvest, unearths the potent force of nostalgia as a tool of agency and resilience. Furthermore, the work's emphasis on women's voices provides a poignant counterpoint to the dominant narratives of the Nakba, illuminating the gendered dimensions of displacement and the enduring power of motherhood in shaping both the colonized and the colonizer.

Mornings in Jenin emerges as a haunting lament, a literary echo of the Palestinian diaspora. It amplifies the marginalized voice of the colonized, delving into the abyss of displacement, loss, and longing. The novel unravels the tapestry of Spivak's ‘subalternity’, a marginalized people cast aside by the oppressive hand and hegemony of Zionist colonialism. By seamlessly

weaving postcolonial literary threads into the discourse of subalternity, Abulhawa explores the profound questions of identity, language, place, belonging, and return that plague the exiled Palestinian. *Mornings in Jenin*, a poignant narrative, amplifies the silenced voices of the Palestinian people. Through the lens of Amal, the protagonist, the novel offers a nuanced exploration of Palestinian subalternity, illuminating the struggles of displacement, occupation, and oppression endured by the inhabitants of the Jenin refugee camp.

Mornings in Jenin fills a significant void in the grand narrative of the Nakba, enriching both the aesthetic and political dimensions of Palestinian fiction. By centering women's experiences, the novel amplifies the voices of those historically marginalized and subjugated. As Loomba (2015) observes, "there was little attempt to locate [women] as subjects within the colonial struggle" (p.214). Abulhawa's narrative challenges patriarchal norms and the oppressive weight of occupation, foregrounding the agency of Palestinian women. By deploying nostalgia as a potent tool of resistance, the novel juxtaposes idyllic pasts with the harsh realities of the present, underscoring the enduring power of memory and the relentless pursuit of justice.

The novel inaugurates in the verdant landscapes of pre-Nakba Palestine, tracing the lineage of the Abulheja family, rooted in the idyllic village of 'Ein Hod. As generations of Palestinian fellaheen tenderly coaxed life from the fertile soil, harvesting olives and figs beneath the sun-drenched sky, a cataclysmic storm descended upon their tranquil existence in 1948. The Zionist invasion uprooted the family, casting them adrift in the harsh realities of the Jenin refugee camp and the vast expanse of the diaspora; and the village of 'Ein Hod emerges as a hallowed site of memory, a place where longing and resilience intertwine.

Dalia Abulheja, a tragic figure etched into the annals of the Nakba, embodies the profound human cost of displacement. Her defiant spirit and maternal instinct are maliciously probed as invading forces snatch her child, leaving an indelible scar upon her soul. As Dalia descends into the twilight of dementia, her story remains a haunting reminder of the enduring trauma of displacement and loss of the Palestinian people. Dalia emerges as a beacon of female agency and resistance, a figure who defies the constraints imposed upon her by both patriarchal and colonial forces.

[Dalia]'s bravery during the war would later be invoked as the essence of a fellaha's fortitude. She refused to flee. She had been pushed off her land once when Ismael was lost, and she had resolved not to let it happen again. ... [S]he would not let the Jews take away the only home her daughter knew. (MJ, p.68)

Another feature of Palestinian resistance is "the quality of 'steadfastness' or 'resilience' ... who may possess no other form of agency than their simple refusal to give in" (Ball, 2012, p.37). Dalia, a beacon of resistance, embodies the indomitable spirit of Palestinian women. She defies the colonial narrative, challenging the notion of their passivity. As she steps beyond domestic confines, she shatters stereotypes, asserting her agency in the face of oppression. Her resilience, a testament to the strength of the human spirit, illuminates the forgotten histories of women who have shaped the Palestinian struggle.

Susan Abulhawa, a Palestinian-American woman, writer, and activist, imbues *Mornings in Jenin* with the poignant echoes of the Palestinian diaspora. Challenging the dominant historical narrative, Abulhawa elevates the voices of women, often marginalized. She illuminates the plight of the Nakba generation, women doubly burdened by the weight of patriarchy and colonialism. Dalia, a central character, embodies such resilience, navigating a landscape

marked by domination and hegemony. By subverting conventional gender roles and colonial tropes, Abulhawa offers a 'nuanced' perspective on the Palestinian struggle. Her work is a testament to the enduring human spirit, a defiant cry against injustice, and a call for empathy and solidarity.

Within the bleak confines of the refugee camp, Dalia gives birth to Amal, a young woman destined to become the novel's poignant narrator. Born into a world scarred by displacement and fragmentation, Amal's life unfurls against the backdrop of the Nakba's enduring shadow. She witnesses the 1967 occupation, the horrific Sabra and Shatila massacres, and the devastating assault on the Jenin refugee camp in 2002, tragic events that claim her life. By chronicling the enduring legacy of the Nakba, Abulhawa illuminates the parallel displacements and ruptures that continue to scar Palestinian lives. Dalia and Amal's consciousnesses serve as powerful conduits, amplifying the voices of Palestinian women who have stood defiant against the oppressive weight of the settler-colonial regime.

Hailing from the harsh confines of a refugee camp, Amal's childhood was etched with the scars of Israeli occupation. Curfews cast long shadows, and the sharp sting of bullets marred her tender frame. Yet, amidst the bleakness, a flicker of life persisted till the second occupation descended upon Palestine, plunging the nation into further turmoil. Amal's world shattered; her father lost, her brother imprisoned, and her mother's life prematurely extinguished by grief. The novel delves into the depths of this collective trauma, tracing the physical, emotional, and national wounds inflicted upon Amal and her family. Despite the darkness, a spark of resilience ignited within her. As a young girl, she was sent to an orphanage in Jerusalem, where she flourished academically, ultimately earning a scholarship to America.

Driven by desperation and the allure of a brighter future, Amal, a young Palestinian orphan, embarked on a journey across continents. A scholarship, a beacon of hope amidst the bleakness of her existence, offered a chance to escape the confines of the refugee camp and the weight of her past. As she pondered her fate, she questioned, "Who was I, indeed? A pathetic orphan, stateless and poor, living off charity;" (MJ, p.159) a question that resonates with Said's (2001) 'reflections on exile.' Here, Amal's narrative starts to mirror the collective Palestinian experience of displacement and exile. A border-crosser and diasporic figure, she navigated the labyrinthine paths of a foreign land, grappling with feelings of inadequacy and alienation. Her journey, a poignant reflection of the Palestinian plight, is a testament to the enduring human spirit. In this regard, Said (2001) comments: "a life of exile moves according to a different calendar, and is less seasonal and settled than life at home. Exile is life led outside habitual order" (p.186).

Abulhawa, drawing from her own experiences, breathes life into Amal, a character who embodies the complexities of the Palestinian diaspora. Both women, bound by shared loss and displacement, navigate the tension between tradition and modernity, belonging and alienation. Amal's journey, a poignant echo of the Palestinian struggle, is marked by the bittersweet nostalgia of the past and the uncertain promise of the future. As she traverses the landscapes of memory and exile, the echoes of her homeland resonate within her soul, a constant reminder of her identity and her purpose. Her ultimate act of defiance, a return to Palestine, is a testament to the enduring power of hope and the indomitable spirit of the Palestinian people. Tragically, Amal's life is cut short by Israeli aggression, her untimely death a poignant reminder of the human cost of occupation and violence. Yet, her legacy lives on,

inspiring her daughter to carry the torch of resistance, ensuring that Amal's story will forever echo through the corridors of history.

According to Homi Bhabha, recalling colonial oppression “is never a quiet act of introspection or retrospection. It is a painful re-remembering, a putting together of the dismembered past to make sense of the trauma of the present” (2004, p.90). The specter of the Nakba looms large over Jenin, its psychological scars as enduring as the physical ones as Amal reflects, “like the scar beneath my hand, the past was still with me.” (MJ, p.173). Amal, a character haunted by the past, bears the weight of displacement. 1948, a year of profound loss and dispossession, continues to shape the Palestinian experience. The sense of the endlessness of the Nakba haunts the novel’s narrative, calling it “that year without end” (MJ, p.43), “that endless year of 1948” (MJ, p.293). The year 1948 - she states, “fell from the calendar into exile... instead becoming an infinite mist of one moment in history.” (MJ, p.35) - becomes a perpetual state of limbo that haunts the Palestinian consciousness as a frozen moment and constant reminder of a stolen homeland and broken dreams. Confined within the temporal and spatial boundaries of the Nakba, Palestinians are condemned to an endless state of exile. By reclaiming this narrative, Abulhawa challenges dominant historical discourses and restores the Palestinian perspective.

In the dawn of the Nakba, a tender bond bloomed, a testament to a time when coexistence flourished. Hasan and Ari, a Palestinian and a Jewish boy, forged a friendship amidst the bustling market, a beacon of hope in an increasingly divided world. Abulhawa challenges the prevailing narrative, painting a portrait of harmony shattered by the forces of history. A poignant reminder of a lost innocence, their story echoes through the ages, a haunting lament for a future that could have been.

Abulhawa's construction of otherness, rooted in her diasporic identity, reflects a moral humanism that transcends national boundaries. Her ability to inhabit what Homi Bhabha calls, the idea of a ‘third space of enunciation’ (2004, p.54) allows her to recognize the humanity of even the oppressor voicing Israeli characters. However, while this hybridity discourse offers a path towards reconciliation, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of such an approach in the context of ongoing oppression. The unequal power dynamics between colonizer and colonized necessitate a more nuanced understanding of the complexities of reconciliation. Ashcroft et al. (2007) argue that a limitation of hybridity discourse is its tendency to oversimplify complex cultural interactions implying that “By stressing the transformative cultural, linguistic and political impacts on both the colonized and the colonizer, it has been regarded as replicating assimilationist policies by masking or ‘whitewashing’ cultural difference.” (p.109)

The assimilationist narrative of hybridity is disrupted by the colonial reality in Palestine. Hasan and Ari's friendship highlights this tension. While Ari, a Jewish immigrant, naively suggests a harmonious coexistence, Hasan exposes the underlying power imbalance. Their contrasting fates – Ari's prosperity in the nascent Israeli state and Hasan's forced displacement and eventual death – underscore the harsh realities of colonial dispossession. Abulhawa's novel, while maintaining a clear humanist perception, does not shy away from the historical truth of violence, domination and oppression.

The seductive allure of hybridity risks obscuring the enduring struggle against colonial oppression. *Mornings in Jenin*, a testament to Palestinian resilience, challenges the facile notion of harmonious coexistence. As Gandhi cautions, hybridity may not be the panacea for systemic

injustice contends that “if the language of hybridity is to retain any seriously political meaning, it must first concede that for some oppressed peoples, in some circumstances, the fight is simply not over. Hybridity is not the only enlightened response to oppression” (p.136). In the Palestinian context, where power imbalances persist, a more nuanced approach is imperative. For Spivak “essentialism is ... used strategically, to bypass or acknowledge difference” (2005, p.477). By embracing strategic essentialism, Palestinians can reclaim their historical identity and resist the erasure of their narrative. This approach, rooted in the shared essence of the nation, stands as a bulwark against the forces of colonial domination.

Furthermore, Abulhawa paints a nostalgic portrait of the lost Palestinian homeland, a canvas imbued with the idyllic hues of the pre-Nakba era. By romanticizing the simple pleasures of village life, she asserts Palestinian rootedness in the land. This postcolonial nostalgia, as theorized by Walder (2011), is nuanced by those “whose links with earlier times and places have been severed by migration or displacement,” and this is no not merely longing for the past but also a defiant act against colonial appropriation. (pp.2-3)

Abulhawa's nostalgic portrayal of the idyllic Palestinian village of Ein Hod serves as a counterpoint to the distorted colonial narrative; “a small village east of Haifa lived quietly on figs and olives, open frontiers and sunshine ... The moon hung low, like a buckle fastening earth and sky, just a sliver of promise shy of being full. Waking limbs stretched, water splashed away sleep, hopeful eyes widened” (MJ, p.3). This romanticized depiction gave nostalgia a sense of restoration “signify[ing] a return to the original stasis [where] the past is a value for the present;” according to Boym's concept of restorative nostalgia. (2001, p.49). By evoking a sense of longing for a bygone era, Abulhawa resists the colonial project of displacement and asserts the enduring presence of Palestinian identity as a form of resistance.

The weight of trauma births a potent nostalgia, a tool of remembrance and resistance. Haj Salem, the village's griot, weaves tales of the past, bridging the gap between generations. His nostalgic recollections, imbued with both pain and longing, ensure that the collective memory of the village endures. “...he would weave dynamic accounts of life and past events with such intricate clarity that Palestine and all her villages, many long since razed by Israel, would come alive in [Amal's] mind as if [she] had lived there [her]self. (MJ, p.78) Nostalgia, a balm for the wounds of displacement, becomes a weapon forged against oblivion. Haj Salem, the village's griot, weaves a tapestry of memory, binding generations past and present. This act of remembrance, a form of postmemory, ensures that the collective memory of the village endures, defying the colonizer's attempts to erase Palestinian history. By invoking nostalgia, Abulhawa charts a course through the desolate landscapes of exile, asserting the Palestinian right to return and reclaim their lost homeland. It is a defiant act against the forces of oblivion, a testament to the indomitable spirit of a people determined to resist and survive.

Mornings in Jenin weaves a tapestry of nostalgia, a counter-narrative to the colonial erasure of Palestinian history. The novel's heart beats with the rhythm of the land, the rhythm of agrarian life. The simple act of harvesting figs, lemons, and olives becomes a profound act of resistance, a reclamation of a stolen heritage. Yahya Abulheja's joy upon returning to his ancestral land, a land etched into his soul, underscores the deep-rooted connection between Palestinians and their soil; “He was so happy. He just unwrapped a bundle of figs, lemons, grapes, carobs, and olives in the middle of town as though he were bringing a million gold dinars. ... Those fruits of forty generations of toil went down like the elixir of Palestine, like the nectar of her centuries” (MJ, p.45). This profound attachment, shared by generations of fellaheen, was a

source of immense pain and humiliation during the Nakba. Fanon (1963) description of how colonizers often portrayed colonized peoples as “torpid creatures, wasted by fevers, obsessed by ancestral customs” (p.51) asserts how Abulhawa's narrative challenges the colonial gaze, painting a vivid picture of a people irrevocably bound to their homeland.

Abulhawa's nostalgic narrative, a poignant elegy to lost lands, evokes the agrarian roots of the Palestinian people. Through her evocative descriptions of carefully cultivated landscapes and groves, she illuminates a past filled with beauty and resilience. This nostalgic longing serves as a powerful tool, challenging the present-day reality of solitude and forsakenness. Amal's awareness adrifts in a sea of memories, ponders the weight of loss, the sting of displacement, and the enduring hope that flickers within her soul stating, [T]he memory of that morning's landscape takes my breath away now. It was the picturesque backdrop of my parents' lives ... Trees like beckoning grandparents, hundreds of years old, wrinkled and stooped with heavy arms that stretched to every direction, as if in prayer.” (MJ, p.117)

Abulhawa paints a poignant portrait of a people deeply rooted in their land. Piterberg notes, “the land, too, was condemned to an exile so long as there was no Jewish sovereignty over it: it lacked any meaningful or authentic history, awaiting redemption with the return of the Jews” (2001, p.32). The ancient trees, silent sentinels of the past, bear witness to generations of Palestinian toil and resilience. Through her evocative storytelling, Abulhawa reclaims the narrative, asserting the enduring connection between Palestinians and their ancestral homeland.

Amal's exile is haunted by the specter of her homeland. Even in the heart of a bustling city, the echoes of Jenin resound, transforming familiar landscapes into uncanny reflections of the past. The ancient olive trees, symbols of resilience and endurance, bridge the chasm between the past and the present. These living monuments, rooted deep in the earth, bear witness to centuries of Palestinian history.

The trees had lost their leaves to winter's chill and the silver wood of olive trees stood bare like colossal ancient hands, the gnarly and twisted guardians of time reaching from the earth, patiently resigned to wait for the ripe season. Homes, some centuries old, with dense vines hugging their masonry, dotted the hillsides, and shepherds moved about with their herds. (MJ, p.113)

The ancient olive trees, gnarled and wise, stand as sentinels of the land, their roots delving deep into the heart of Palestinian history. These verdant guardians, entwined with the lives of generations, offer solace and sustenance, transforming the landscape into a living memory. For the displaced Palestinians, these trees are beacons of hope, a tangible connection to a lost paradise. Through these nostalgic recollections, Abulhawa challenges the Zionist narrative, reclaiming the Palestinian past and asserting the right to a future rooted in the land. *Mornings in Jenin* stands as a literary testament, a defiant act that resurrects the memory of the Palestinian people's enduring struggle against Zionist colonialism.

A venture into the intricate tapestry of Abulhawa's literary landscape reveals the intertwined threads of resistance, marginalization, nostalgia, and displacement. The novel's nostalgic undercurrent emerges as a potent force of reclamation, a balm that soothes the wounds inflicted by the Nakba. By invoking the symbolic tropes of agrarian life and a profound connection to the colonized homeland, *Mornings in Jenin* inscribes Palestinian history and culture into the fabric of time. This act of remembrance challenges the silencing attempts of

colonial narratives, amplifying the voice of Palestinian nostalgia. Moreover, the novel delves into the experiences of Palestinian women, shattering the monolithic image of passive victimhood. It foregrounds their narratives, asserting their agency and historical significance. By examining the debilitating impact of colonial oppression on displaced women, the novel reveals the intricate interplay between personal and national struggles. *Mornings in Jenin* ultimately reveals the interconnectedness of the national, the feminist, and the personal, underscoring the intersectional nature of the Palestinian struggle for liberation.

Displacement, Resistance and Identity in Yahya al-Sinwar's *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* 'Thorns and Carnations': A postcolonial Reading

Do we exist? What proof do we have? The further we get from Palestine of our past, the more precarious our status, the more disrupted our being, the more intermittent our presence" (p.34).

– Edward Said, *After the Last Sky* (1986), p.34

Gaza, a city of shifting sands, metamorphoses ceaselessly, adapting to the tempestuous tides of history. A city of refugees, its identity is as fluid as the sea, oscillating between tranquility and chaos, life and death. Once a maritime city, it now stands fortified, a bastion of resistance. Yet, beneath its hardened exterior, a resilient spirit persists, weaving a tapestry of hope amidst the despair. Al-Sinwar's *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* captures this paradoxical existence with a raw, unfiltered authenticity.

From the very outset of the text and throughout its unfolding narrative, the author deftly directs our gaze toward the multitude of individuals striving upon the sacred land of Palestine. Through richly drawn characters and evocative stories, he elucidates with remarkable clarity the geographical and emotional landscapes that shape their experiences. The narrative chronicles the trajectory of events spanning over three tumultuous decades, from the profound defeat of 1967 to the fervent eruption of the Al-Aqsa Intifada in 2000, revealing how each incident intertwines with the lives and aspirations of the Palestinian people.

A poignant reflection on the Palestinian struggle, *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* delves deep into the historical documentary of the national movement. It traverses the labyrinthine history of Palestinian aspiration beginning in the pre-1967 era tracing the tumultuous journey through the lens of a captive combatant. Immersed in the trenches of resistance, the narrator offers a nuanced exploration of the societal and psychological currents that shaped the Palestinian people during this period. With keen observation and introspection, *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* captures the essence of a generation caught in the throes of conflict, posing profound questions about identity, purpose, and the enduring spirit of defiance.

Written in the depths of despair and under the shadow of imprisonment, the author grapples with the stark reality of his circumstances, compelled to delve into the recesses of his memory. He meticulously reconstructs the intricate details of the life led by "Ahmed," the novel's protagonist and insightful narrator, as a means to navigate the weight of time pressing upon him. This act of recollection becomes a desperate plea to reclaim agency amid the monotony and forgetfulness that imprisonment fosters, reflecting a deeper struggle to hold onto the aspirations of life that persist beyond the confining walls. Such a narrative choice underscores the complexities of resistance and identity within a postcolonial framework, illuminating the profound interplay between memory, trauma, and the enduring human spirit in the face of systemic oppression.

Edward Said's in *The World, the Text and the Critic* (1983) states "texts are worldly, to some degree they are events, and, even when they appear to deny it, they are nevertheless a part of the social world, human life, and of course the historical moments in which they are located and interpreted." (p.4) Hence, *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* appears as a testament to the indomitable human spirit offering a candid and unvarnished glimpse into the marginalized existence of a political prisoner. A fusion of journalistic rigor and literary artistry, it eschews sensationalism, instead presenting a sobering portrait of life behind bars. Though rooted in personal narrative, the work transcends the individual to explore the universal themes of oppression, resistance, and the enduring power of the human spirit. Echoes of literary giants such as Ghassan Kanafani reverberate within its pages, underscoring the timeless nature of the subaltern struggle.

The prison, a microcosm of societal power dynamics, confines the subaltern figure of the political prisoner. Silenced and marginalized, this individual challenges the dominant narrative by offering a counter-discourse through the novel. Rather than focusing solely on the physical imprisonment, the novel extends its gaze outward, treating confinement as a catalyst for introspection and resistance. It unveils the untold stories of the Palestinian struggle, a subaltern narrative often overlooked or misrepresented. Alongside works like "The Thorn and The Carnation," this novel contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the Palestinian people. As a documentary novel, it meticulously chronicles the heroic acts of guerrilla fighters, providing an accurate historical record of a pivotal era marked by complexity and dynamism.

Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful whispers a chilling truth: liberation lies not in escape, but in the very heart of annihilation. It transcends the confines of partisan politics, embracing a fervent patriotism that knows no ideological boundaries. Its narrative traverses the globe, from the vast expanse of continents to the besieged sands of Gaza. It evokes the sensory tapestry of this beleaguered land, its gritty trenches, its makeshift shelters, and its indomitable people. It even delves into the subtle metamorphosis of their appearance, as they transition from passive observers to active architects of their destiny. Shackled by injustice, the author found solace in the unfettered world of fiction. A captive of the Israeli prison system for two decades, he defied his captors by crafting narratives that challenged their oppressive silence especially in the absence of Palestinian voices and narratives.

The postcolonial Bildungsroman, a subversive genre, challenges the linear trajectory of traditional coming-of-age narratives. By appropriating and subverting the imperial Bildungsroman's tropes, it exposes the fractured and precarious nature of identity formation under colonial domination. José Santiago Fernández Vázquez (2002) asserts, "the reasons why postcolonial writers turn to the Bildungsroman is the desire to incorporate the master codes of imperialism into the text, in order to sabotage them more effectively" (p.86). This literary strategy, akin to Bhabha's concept of mimicry (2004), allows marginalized voices to resist and reimagine the future, highlighting the enduring power of the written word in the face of oppression.

Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful opens with a haunting childhood memory of young Ahmed, a boy of only five. It is 1967, a year marked by war, and Ahmed watches his father toil beneath their home, digging a small sanctuary into the earth. This scene brings the plight of Palestinian refugees vividly to life—crowded into makeshift camps; their only defense from relentless attacks an improvised network of tunnels offering frail protection. These early shelters

resonate with the complex, subterranean paths developed over decades under occupation underscoring the persistence of survival strategies woven into the history of the Palestinians who hide as a means of hope beneath the earth's surface.

In the shadowed hollow of their cramped shelter in al-Shati, the family clings to one another, days slipping by as they listen intently to a crackling radio stationed near the entrance. News of the 1967 defeat fills the small space, mingling with their breath and unspoken prayers. They wait, hoping against hope for a victory that never comes, longing to reclaim the homes they lost in 1948, a return that feels as elusive as the light outside.

In the opening of his novel, Sinwar audaciously asserts that the narrative is not anchored to any single individual, yet every event within its pages resonates with the experiences of all Palestinians in Gaza, echoing both their storied past and their present struggles.

This is not my personal story, nor is it the story of any one individual, though all its events are real. Each event or set of events belongs to this or that Palestinian. The only fiction in this work lies in transforming it into a novel centered around specific characters to meet the form and conventions of a novel. Beyond that, everything is true – things I experienced myself and much of which I heard from the mouths of those who lived through it, as well as from their families and neighbors over many decades on the beloved land of Palestine. (TC, P. 2)

Yet, he cleverly refrains from fully extricating the tale from the tapestry of his own life, allowing flickers of personal truth to illuminate the story. The narrator, a boy mirroring Sinwar's own age, embodies the essence of countless souls who, in the tumult of the 1967 war, sought refuge in fragile trenches beneath the weary floors of their homes in Khan Younis camp, transforming their intimate struggles into a collective memory of survival and resilience.

The absence of the father and uncle in the novel starkly illuminates the emergence of a new generation of Palestinians, whose political awareness was forged in the crucible of the 1967 defeat and the ensuing Israeli occupation of the West Bank, Gaza, and East Jerusalem—a generation that Sinwar himself embodies.

The state of resistance in the Gaza Strip was significantly stronger than that in the West Bank, primarily due to the presence of a battalion of fighters known as the Palestinian Liberation Army, established as a military force for the Palestine Liberation Organization. This creation was largely a response by Arab regimes to alleviate their burden of responsibility towards Palestine. However, following the 1967 war, this army fragmented; many were martyred, while others—constituting the majority—fled to Egypt or were expelled there. A portion remained in Gaza and formed the Popular Liberation Forces, which marked the beginning of organized resistance. (TC, P. 39)

At this juncture, Palestinian resistance appeared politically and geographically estranged from Gaza, which one fateful summer morning in 1967 awoke to find the Egyptian army's encampment near al-Shati eerily deserted, long before the somber news of defeat reached its shores. In *Blaming the Victims* (1988), Said notes that the Zionist “won the political battle for Palestine in the international world in which ideas, representation, rhetoric and images were at issue” (p.1). Sinwar vividly captures a harrowing scene that he may have witnessed: the Israeli army, having commandeered military vehicles and tanks still emblazoned with Egyptian flags, ruthlessly opening fire on the Palestinians who fled toward them, seeking refuge and aid. This moment underscores the tragic irony of their predicament—caught in the crossfire of a conflict that rendered their pleas for help a mere echo in the chaos of war. By

1967, over half of Gaza's inhabitants – approximately half a million souls – had been replaced, uprooted from their homes by Israelis.

The intricate details of life in the camp during this era resonate painfully with the grim realities faced by many in present-day Gaza, often depicted in international reports as “catastrophic.” In Sinwar’s novel, the Gaza of his childhood emerges as a bleak wasteland – a conservative, insular refugee community where makeshift homes are likened to “chicken coops,” their tiled roofs offering little sanctuary from the relentless rains that pummel the region. The diet is meager, relying heavily on the scant provisions allocated by the United Nations Relief and Works Agency (UNRWA), which typically consist of flour, cooking oil, and an occasional assortment of legumes.

In this harsh existence, long lines snake in front of the solitary water tap installed by UNRWA in the camp’s courtyard, where water is a fleeting resource, available for only a few hours each day. The children, dressed in tattered garments distributed by UNRWA a mere twice a year, find solace in a game of “Arabs and Jews,” where one team embodies the Palestinians (“Arabs”) while the other dons the guise of Israeli occupation soldiers “Jews”. In this stark environment, electricity remains a distant luxury, reserved only for the relatively “well-off,” underscoring the vast chasm between survival and a semblance of normalcy in a land marked by enduring strife.

The author sharply contrasts the economic disparities between Gaza and Hebron, located about 40 miles away. After the occupation, Hebron's economy surged, fueled by Jewish religious tourism to the Ibrahimi Mosque, which diverted Palestinian focus toward production and improved living standards, thereby undermining Fatah's resistance efforts. Amid the rapid defeat of Arab armies by Israel, many Palestinians questioned the feasibility of resistance: “How could a handful of fedayeen stand against such overwhelming force?” (TC, P 32) This pervasive sense of despair lingered in the city’s cafes, long before Hebron evolved into a hotbed of resistance, driven by the children of the 1967 war who would rise against the occupation from the 1980s onward.

In the early 1970s, Palestinians enjoyed the ability to cross into Israel for work, a time marked by the absence of checkpoints, walls, or barriers. Israeli businesses eagerly hired workers from Gaza, the West Bank, and East Jerusalem, drawn to their lower wages and the convenience of exploiting them through grueling hours and minimal benefits. This practice also aimed to quash resistance, stirring considerable controversy among Palestinians. The novel adeptly captures the tension of this scenario, illuminating the complex realities and difficult choices faced by an occupied populace. What initially began as a principled moral stance against working in the territories occupied in 1948 gradually succumbed to the oppressive weight of pervasive poverty that afflicted many in the Gaza Strip.

In the early 1970s, Palestinians found themselves ensnared in a paradox: while they enjoyed a fleeting freedom to traverse into Israel for work – an anomaly in a landscape soon dominated by checkpoints and walls – this apparent liberation belied a more insidious reality. Israeli businesses, lured by the allure of cheaper labor, actively recruited workers from Gaza, the West Bank, and East Jerusalem, exploiting their vulnerability through grueling hours and minimal benefits. This systemic exploitation was not merely an economic arrangement; it was a calculated strategy aimed at stifling resistance, igniting fierce controversy within Palestinian society.

The matter should be discussed from the perspective that there are homes in need of a loaf of bread and milk for our children, yet they cannot find it. Working inside Israel, despite its difficulties and bitterness, is viewed by others as a national duty to support our people's resilience in their camps and villages, rather than forcing the necessity to migrate. Practically speaking, the men of resistance, especially in the refugee camps, such as those in the Shati camp, considered this a crime. (TC, P. 49)

The novel intricately captures the tension embedded in this dynamic, laying bare the agonizing choices confronting an occupied populace. Initially, many Palestinians adhered to a resolute moral and political refusal to engage with the territories seized in 1948, their resistance a testament to their struggle for identity and autonomy. Yet, as the relentless pressure of pervasive poverty intensified, this unwavering resolve began to erode, revealing the complex interplay between ideology and survival. The societal controversy surrounding participation in the Israeli economy reflects the internal divisions that often arise in colonized communities, where conflicting identities and loyalties collide under the weight of systemic oppression.

This narrative echoes the shifting landscape of power and control, a precursor to the physical barriers that would later define their existence. The early freedom of movement became an illusion, a temporary reprieve from the looming shadows of structural violence. As individuals were compelled to compromise their principles in the face of dire economic circumstances, the novel underscores a profound truth of the postcolonial experience: the relentless struggle for dignity often exists in the interstices of exploitation and resistance, where survival and integrity are in constant negotiation.

In this complex tapestry, the Palestinians' plight serves as a poignant reminder of the enduring legacies of colonialism, illustrating how economic dependencies perpetuate cycles of despair and thwart the aspirations of a people yearning for self-determination. Their story is not merely one of victimhood; it is a testament to resilience in the face of overwhelming odds, a narrative of struggle that speaks to the heart of postcolonial discourse – where the pursuit of agency, identity, and justice remains an unyielding quest against the backdrop of a fractured landscape.

The struggle for education in the Gaza Strip during the 1970s can be closely analyzed through the lens of postcolonial theory, particularly using Frantz Fanon's notions of liberation and identity formation. Fanon argued that education is a critical tool for the oppressed to reclaim their agency and assert their identity in the face of colonial subjugation. The establishment of a local university amid the closure of Egyptian universities exemplifies this principle; it becomes a site of resistance where marginalized voices strive to redefine their existence and assert their right to knowledge.

The struggle for education in the Gaza Strip during the 1970s serves as a powerful testament to postcolonial resistance against colonial oppression. When the rift between Egyptian President Anwar Sadat and the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) closed Egyptian universities to Gaza students, the establishment of a local university became an act of defiance and reclamation of agency. In makeshift tents, students gathered, transforming education into a collective assertion of cultural identity and resilience against displacement. This grassroots initiative challenged the hegemonic narratives of external powers, embodying a critical effort to decolonize knowledge and affirm that learning is a fundamental right.

Moreover, the political dynamics surrounding this struggle underscore the historical injustices that continue to shape contemporary realities. The denial of educational opportunities reveals a strategy of erasure, compelling young Palestinians to transcend the role of passive victims and emerge as architects of their futures. Their commitment to education, driven by a desire for self-determination, underscores a profound truth of postcolonial discourse: that in the face of oppression, the pursuit of knowledge becomes a powerful act of resistance, affirming the strength and resilience of a people determined to reclaim their narrative.

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The narrative goes further to align with Homi K. Bhabha's concept of 'cultural hybridity,' which emphasizes the blending of cultures in the colonial context. The students' gathering in makeshift tents symbolizes a fusion of traditional and modern educational practices, reflecting their resilience and adaptability. This hybrid identity fosters a sense of community and solidarity, essential in the fight against displacement and oppression. Moreover, the educational struggle in Gaza mirrors Edward Said's critiques in 'Orientalism,' where he highlights the importance of challenging the dominant narratives imposed by colonial powers. The grassroots initiative to create a university represents a conscious effort to assert a Palestinian narrative, countering external attempts to erase their cultural identity.

Sinwar seeks not only to chronicle a pivotal moment in the saga of resistance but to transcend the boundaries of traditional historical documentation. In this endeavor, the novel's historical touch becomes more than a mere reflection of bygone events; it evolves into a profound inquiry into the philosophical and moral currents that underpin historical movements. The characters navigate a landscape of ideological struggle, embodying the philosophical dilemmas of their era. This interplay serves as a conduit for exploring the intricate connections between personal convictions and the broader strokes of history. In doing so, the novel not only recounts a historical trajectory but also challenges readers to reflect on the complex interplay between ideology and history, thereby enriching the discourse surrounding resistance and identity.

Through the lens of the son of the refugee camp; Ahmad, the narrative unfolds as a poignant exploration of identity amidst the ruins of colonial violence and displacement. In the confines of the refugee camp, where the specter of his father – a vanished resistance fighter – haunts every shadow, Ahmad grapples with the heavy legacy of loss. His father's absence is not merely a personal tragedy; it epitomizes the broader erasure of agency that countless individuals endure in the wake of systemic oppression. In these harrowing circumstances, Ahmad's world is imbued with a sense of fragmentation, reflecting Frantz Fanon's insights into the psychological toll of colonialism on the individual psyche.

As he navigates the harsh realities of camp life, characterized by poverty and the suffocating weight of cultural expectations, Ahmad's observations reveal a society grappling with its own fractured identity. His mother's fierce dedication to upholding communal honor, particularly regarding the dignity of daughters, underscores the tensions inherent in cultural survival. This

strict adherence to tradition serves as both a protective mechanism and a burden, illustrating how deeply rooted societal norms can shape personal experiences within a colonial context.

Yet, amidst this struggle for identity, moments of solace arise through Ahmad's connection with his grandfather. Their shared prayers and communal gatherings at the mosque become sanctuaries of resistance, embodying Homi K. Bhabha's notion of hybridity. In these sacred spaces, where cultural practices intertwine with spiritual resilience, Ahmad discovers a sense of belonging that transcends the pervasive despair of his surroundings. It is here that the narrative subverts dominant colonial discourses, reclaiming agency and dignity in the face of relentless adversity.

Moreover, the story resonates with Edward Said's critique of Orientalism, as it challenges reductive portrayals of Palestinian refugees within Western narratives. Through Ahmad's intimate experiences, the novel defies simplistic stereotypes, illuminating the complexities of human dignity and resilience that persist against the backdrop of suffering. In this richly woven tapestry, Ahmad's journey serves as a microcosm of the broader postcolonial struggle, articulating the indomitable spirit of those who dare to reclaim their narrative from the shadows of colonial history.

Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful critically examines the Palestinians' complex journey of transforming defeat into a hard-won sense of pride, particularly in the aftermath of the 1970 Battle of Karama, where they successfully repelled the Israeli army. This moment of euphoria is starkly juxtaposed with the pervasive frustration and despair that engulfed Gaza and the West Bank, following a series of disheartening events: the violent clash of Black September with the Jordanians, Egypt's controversial peace agreement with Israel in 1979, the forced exile of resistance fighters from Lebanon after the Israeli invasion in 1982, and the disillusioning Oslo Accords, which many Palestinians perceived as a capitulation rather than a step toward their aspirations for liberation.

These setbacks did not extinguish the Palestinians' resolve; rather, they ignited a fervent determination to keep the struggle alive. Operating with meager resources, they engaged in acts of defiance against occupying forces – wounding or capturing soldiers in an effort to negotiate the release of their comrades held in Israeli prisons. This relentless pursuit of agency highlights the resilience of a people caught in the web of occupation, yet also raises critical questions about the efficacy of their strategies and the implications of ongoing resistance amid shifting political landscapes. The novel aligns with what Said (2001) asserts for Palestinians who have fight and engage in a relentless struggle to reclaim their narrative, to counter the erasure of their history and memory by the dominant Zionist discourse. He concludes, “the greatest battle Palestinians have waged as a people has been over the right to a remembered presence and, with that presence, the right to possess and reclaim a collective historical reality” (p.184).

Conclusion:

Palestinian Fiction: Fractured Destinies versus persistent Identities

[C]ritique may not know the outcomes it wants in advance, but it is, nonetheless, in pursuit of a more truthful truth. (p.x)

– Gandhi, *Postcolonial Theory: A Critical Introduction* (2019), p.x

By summoning the spectral presence of colonial oppression, this study aims to dismantle the dominant narratives that have marginalized the Palestinian struggle. This analysis seeks to expose the biases that have obscured the Palestinian reality, reorienting the Palestinian fictional trajectory and demanding a re-examination of the historical record. By re-narrating the Nakba, this study aims to challenge the oppressive silence that has enveloped the Palestinian experience, offering a counter-narrative that centers Palestinian voices and reclaims their agency asserting their rightful claim to liberation and self-determination. *Mornings in Jenin* and *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful* are powerful narratives that imbued with the raw power of lived experience, challenge dominant narratives and subvert colonial discourse.

This paper repositions contemporary Palestinian fiction within the framework of the Nakba, not only as a historical event but as a dynamic discourse of cultural activism and resistance. The study moves beyond common postcolonial themes of exile and identity to explore deeper political aesthetics around nostalgia, resistance, and trauma. Focusing on two novels, it examines narrative strategies – such as nostalgia and testimonial narration – that shape the Nakba's representation as a site of contested memory.

This research theorizes Palestinian memory as a collaborative and multi-faceted act of witnessing. It calls for a reexamination of Palestine as a colonized landscape within a postcolonial framework, urging for a critical and reflective approach to Palestinian cultural expression. Through a postcolonial lens, we witness Palestinian writers subvert colonial discourse and reclaim their cultural heritage. Nostalgia, a complex and ambivalent force, simultaneously anchors Palestinians to their past and holding back any prosecutions of the colonized part for identity erasure. As Palestinian writers navigate the labyrinthine complexities of identity, memory, and belonging, they offer a powerful critique of the Israeli occupation and its devastating impact on Palestinian society.

These novels foreground the trope of Palestinian rootedness, recreating the idealized image of a harmonious society to counter the Zionist colonial project. By exploring these poetics of rootedness and memory, this study positions such novels a pivotal force of resistance towards the road of liberation. However, this analysis is limited by its focus on *Mornings in Jenin* and *Al-Shawk wa'l Qurunful*. Further exploration of works by Palestinian authors such as Ibtisam Azem, Ghassan Kanafani, Rabai Al-Madhoun, Elias Khoury – and more – could expand the scope of this study and reveal additional dimensions of the Palestinian literary landscape.

The ongoing Israeli occupation continues to shape the Palestinian experience, forcing Palestinians to navigate a complex landscape of violence, displacement, and dispossession. Palestinian literature, however, persists as a beacon of hope, a testament to the resilience of the human spirit. This research reimagines postcolonial studies, expanding its scope to encompass new geographies and activist discourses. By dwelling on the wounds of the past, such fictional texts guard against historical amnesia and inspire future generations to continue the fight for justice and liberation.

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